

DiamondBridge Economics and Business Journal

A Publication of Garden City Premier Business School, Port Harcourt-Nigeria

ISSN 2756-4495(Print); ISSN 2756-4487(Online)

Volume 4, Issue 2, February, 2024

Journal homepage: <https://www.dbebj.com>

Original Research Article

AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL DEEPENING AND AGRICULTURAL GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study empirically assesses the impact of financial deepening on Agricultural sector in Nigeria using time series data from 1990 to 2023. Growth in Agriculture was used to represent Agricultural sector while financial deepening indicators were financial access, financial depth and financial efficiency. Auto regressive distributed lag (ARDL) was used to estimate the models. The empirical result shows while financial access had positive and significant influence on the growth in Agriculture, financial depth was negative and significant, and financial efficiency was positive and insignificant to growth in the sector during the period of study. The study concludes that financial deepening has positive effect on growth in the agricultural sector within the reviewed period. In light of the empirical findings, the following recommendations were made: that CBN should implement policies geared towards enhancing financial inclusion to enable Nigeria citizens and prospective farmers to have easy access to affordable financial services and also to encourage commercial banks to increase credit facilities to both farmers and private sector so as to increase Agricultural production in the Nigerian economy.

Keywords: *Agriculture; Nigerian economy; financial inclusion; farmers*

1.INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In the context of agriculture in Nigeria, financial deepening plays a crucial role in driving growth and development in the sector. Robert C. Williams (1994) defined financial deepening as the increase in the use of financial services and instruments by agricultural household and businesses. Nigeria is a country where agriculture serves as a vital sector contributing significantly to the country's economy, employment and food security. Despite this, the sector faces numerous challenges, with limited access to finance being a major bottleneck. One of the key ways in which financial deepening had impacted agricultural growth in Nigeria is by increasing access to credit and capital for farmers and investors,(Marcel, Fafchamps 2003) With improved access to financial services, farmers are able to invest in modern farming techniques, purchase high-quality inputs, and expand their operations ((Nzotta & Okereke, 2009). This leads to increased productivity and higher yields, ultimately boosting agricultural output and contributing to overall economic growth. A well developed financial system broadens access to funds which promotes

investment and economic growth. This can also be promoted through the introduction of diverse financial reforms and policies.

The depth of the financial system is the measure of the extent of diversified opportunities, access to financial intermediation, quality information and attractive incentives for prudent lending and monitoring (Ewetan & Ike, 2014). Generally, financial deepening measures the ease with which the financial system provides funding for agricultural activities, as well as the extent to which financial services are made available (Gwama.M, 2014). The banking sector and capital market are developed institutions for funding agricultural and industrial development in Nigeria. The extent to which the bank lends to the agricultural sector is influenced by the monetary policies rates vis-à-vis the prevailing interest rates. Furthermore, financial deepening allows farmers to better manage risks associated with agriculture, such as weather fluctuations and price volatility. By accessing insurance products and other risk management tools, farmers are better equipped to withstand shocks and uncertainties, leading to more stable incomes and sustainable agricultural production.

Schumpeter (1934) opined that a well-

functioning financial sector plays an important role in driving real sector which resultantly leads to agricultural growth. In addition, McKinnon and Shaw (1973) advocated for the deepening of the financial sector for improved financial intermediation. This is believed to allow for financial inclusion with its associated benefits for inclusive and agricultural growth. Additionally, financial deepening promotes the adoption of new technologies and innovations in agriculture (Kalirajan K.P, 2013). With access to financial resources, farmers can invest in research and development, adopt new technologies, and improve their farming practices. This leads to increased efficiency, productivity, and competitiveness in the agricultural sector. In Nigeria, the impact of financial deepening on agricultural growth has been significant. The introduction of policies and programs aimed at expanding access to financial services, such as the establishment of agricultural development banks and microfinance institutions, has improved access to credit for small scale farmers and boosted agricultural productivity. Financial deepening in Nigeria has been linked to growth in the agricultural sector. This is because access to

finance can help farmers and agribusinesses to invest in inputs, equipment, and land, which can lead to higher productivity and higher incomes, (Carlos E. Cuevas, 2001). Moreover; increased lending to the agricultural sector can stimulate growth in agricultural output. There are several initiatives and programs in Nigeria that aim to promote financial deepening and growth in agricultural output. For example, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) established the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) to provide credit to farmers and agribusinesses at a low-interest rate. The CBN also established the Anchor Borrowers Program (ABP) to provide credit facilities for smallholder farmers to support the production of crops such as rice, wheat, and maize.

In addition, the Nigerian Incentive-Based Risk Sharing System for Agricultural Lending (NIRSAL) was established to provide technical assistance and risk-sharing facilities to banks willing to lend to the agricultural sector. The program aims to increase access to finance in agriculture and reduce the perceived risks associated with lending to the sector. Despite the growing advocacy for financial deepening in Nigeria, the level of progress achieved in the past years raised many controversies in recent times on the intended and desired policy goal. Although numerous

attempts have been made in the past to explain the effectiveness of financial deepening, the emphasis has been on economic growth with little or no attention given to growth in agricultural sector, this study seeks to examine how financial deepening contributes to agricultural growth in the Nigeria.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The impact of financial deepening on agricultural growth in Nigeria remains largely unknown and understudied. While there are existing studies on the relationship between financial development and economic growth in Nigeria, there is a scarcity of comprehensive studies specifically focusing on the link between financial deepening and agricultural growth in the country. Thomas Reardon (2005) in his study titled “financial deepening and agricultural transformation” opined that increase in the use of financial deepening services and instruments can support agricultural modernization and commercialization. Given the critical importance of agriculture to the Nigerian economy, understanding the extent to which access to financial services and products influence the performance and growth of the agricultural sector is crucial for policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders. It is imperative to

investigate the potential mechanisms through which financial deepening can drive agricultural productivity, enhance access to credit and insurance for farmers, as well as promote investment in modern farming practices and technologies.

The study by Osa-Afina and Kelikume (2015) stated that the banking sector reform and credit supply to agricultural sector have positive effect on agricultural output in Nigeria. According to them the reforms and measures implemented by the monetary authorities particularly CBN in Nigeria are beginning to yield positive result and the degree of financial deepening has improved immensely. The lack of empirical evidence and comprehensive analysis on the impact of financial deepening on agricultural growth in Nigeria presents a gap in literature that needs to be addressed. This study aims to fill this gap by assessing the relationship between financial deepening and agricultural growth, identifying the key factors influencing this relationship, and providing possible policy recommendations to leverage the potential benefits of financial deepening for the agricultural sector in Nigeria.

1.2 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study was to examine the impact of financial deepening on agricultural growth in Nigeria between 1990 and 2023. Specifically, the study was design to:

- i. examine the effect of financial depth (FD) on agricultural growth in Nigeria.
- ii. determine the effect of Financial access (FA) on agricultural growth in Nigeria.
- iii. ascertain the effect of financial efficiency (FE) on agricultural growth in Nigeria

1.4 Research Hypotheses

The hypotheses for this study are stated in the null forms as follows:

- i. H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between financial depth (FD) and agricultural growth in Nigeria.
- ii. H_{02} : Financial Access (FA) does not significantly affect agricultural growth in Nigeria.
- iii. H_{03} : Financial Efficiency (FE) does not have any significant effect on agricultural growth in Nigeria

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Financial Deepening

Thorsten Beck (2009) defined financial

deepening as the process of improving the efficiency and effectiveness of financial system. Financial deepening also mean the expansion of financial services and products within an economy, leading to increased access to financial services, greater financial intermediation, and improved efficiency in the allocation of resources. This can involve the development of new financial products, such as loans, savings accounts, insurance, and investment options, as well as the expansion of financial institutions, financial markets and networks, (Robert C. Merton, 1992) Financial deepening plays a crucial role in promoting economic growth, reducing poverty, and fostering financial stability within an economy. By expanding access to financial services and products, individuals and businesses are better able to participate in the economy, invest in their futures, and improve their financial well-being. According to Schumpeter (1934), banks channel savings to firms and entrepreneurs who offer feasible and profitable investment projects. By doing so, banks and financial institutions do affect economic growth and development. Some of the key initiatives and developments contributing to financial deepening in

Nigeria include:

1. The establishment of the National Financial Inclusion Strategy (NFIS) in 2012, which aims to drive financial inclusion and expand access to financial services for underserved populations.
2. The introduction of agency banking, mobile money services, and digital financial solutions, which have helped to improve access to banking services for remote and underserved areas in Nigeria.
3. The licensing of Payment Service Banks (PSBs) by the Central Bank of Nigeria, allowing non-bank entities to provide limited financial services, further expanding access to financial services in rural and underserved areas.
4. The implementation of credit bureau services, which help to improve credit information sharing and reduce credit risk for lenders, promoting access to credit for individuals and businesses.
5. The promotion of financial literacy programs and consumer protection measures to educate Nigerians on financial products and services, and to safeguard their interests in financial transactions.

2.1.2 Financial Inclusion

Financial inclusion is seen and defined as a state in which all the people of a

particular nation have complete access to appropriate desired financial products and services in order to manage their money effectively (Nwanne, 2015). Financial inclusion also means to the widespread access to financial services and products among individuals and businesses, particularly those who are traditionally underserved or excluded from the financial system. This includes access to basic banking services, credit, insurance, and other financial tools that can help individuals and businesses manage their finances, build assets, and improve their economic well-being, (Svetlana Andrianova, 2019). Centre for Financial Inclusion (2013), sees financial inclusion as a state in which all people who use financial service have access to a complement of quality financial services, provided at affordable prices in a convenient manner and with dignity for the clients. Financial inclusion ensures the ease of access, availability and usage of formal financial system by all members of the economy (Onaolapo, 2015).

2.1.3 Financial Depth

Financial depth refers to the size and overall development of a country's financial system. It measures the level of financial intermediation, including the availability of financial institutions, the

range of financial products and services offered, and the overall depth of financial markets, (CBN statistical bulletin, 2023). A deeper financial system typically indicates a higher level of financial intermediation, which can provide greater support to economic activities, including agriculture, (Robert King, 1993). In the context of agricultural growth in Nigeria, improving financial depth can lead to increased access to credit, savings, insurance, and other financial services for farmers and agribusinesses, enabling them to invest in their operations and drive productivity. The indicators of a country financial depth are expressed in terms of the following:

- Private sector credit to Gross domestic product (GDP).
- Financial institutions (Banks) assets to gross domestic product (GDP).
- Insurance companies assets to gross domestic product (GDP).
- Pension fund assets to gross domestic product (GDP).
- Other non bank financial institutions assets to gross domestic product.
- Money supply (M2) to gross domestic product (GDP).

- Total Deposits to gross domestic product (GDP).

2.1.4 Financial Access

Financial access refers to the ability of individuals, households, and businesses to access and use financial services and products, (Svetlana Andrianova, 2019). This includes access to savings accounts, credit facilities, insurance products, and payment services, (Anjali Kumar, 2020). Improving financial access is crucial for promoting inclusive growth and reducing poverty, as it enables underserved populations, including smallholder farmers, to participate in formal financial systems and benefit from financial services. In the context of agricultural growth in Nigeria, enhancing financial access can help unlock the economic potential of smallholder farmers, empower women and marginalized groups, and promote financial inclusion and resilience within the agricultural sector. The indicators of a country financial access are expressed in terms of the following:

- Banks accounts per 1,000 adults
- Banks branches per 100,000 adults
- % of firms with a line of credit or bank loan.

- % of small firms i.e. SMEs with a line of credit or bank loan
- % of persons whose receive deposits in forms of credit transactions
- % of persons who have ATM cards or access to internet banking services.
- Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) per 100,000 adults

2.1.5 Financial Efficiency

Financial efficiency refers to the effectiveness and productivity of a country's financial system in allocating resources and facilitating economic activities, (Patrick Honohan, 2015). An efficient financial system ensures that capital flows smoothly between savers and borrowers, investments are allocated to the most productive uses, and risks are managed effectively,(Asli Demirguc_kunt, 2008). In the context of agricultural growth, financial efficiency can lead to better resource allocation within the sector, increased access to credit for farmers at competitive rates, and the effective management of risks, ultimately supporting sustainable agricultural development. The indicators financial institution efficiency is measured in terms of the following:

- Net interest margin

- Financial institutions lending to deposits spread
- Non-interest income to total income
- Overhead costs (% of total assets) and
- Profitability (return on assets, return on equity) and
- Credit to Government and state owned enterprises to GDP.

2.1.6 Financial Deepening and Growth in Agricultural Sector.

Financial deepening and growth in Nigeria's agricultural sector are interconnected and play a crucial role in the country's overall economic development. Financial deepening refers to the expansion of financial services and products within an economy, leading to increased access to financial services, greater financial intermediation, and improved efficiency in resource allocation, (Marcel F. 2003). In the context of Nigeria's agricultural sector, financial deepening is essential for promoting agricultural growth, enhancing productivity, and ensuring food security.

According to Usman (2006), agriculture is the largest employer of labor as it serves as a source of livelihood to two-third of Nigerian population. Not minding these factors, the contribution

of agricultural sector output to the entire Nigerian economic growth has been declining continuously since the oil boom of 1970.

Loyaza (2000) opined that a deep and efficient financial system can contribute robustly to sustain economic growth through growth in agricultural output. Efforts towards financial deepening in Nigeria's agricultural sector have been made through various initiatives and programs aimed at increasing access to finance for farmers, promoting investment in agricultural value chains, and enhancing financial inclusion among rural communities. Some key factors that contribute to financial deepening in the agricultural sector in Nigeria include:

1. Access to credit: Access to credit is crucial for smallholder farmers and agribusinesses to invest in inputs, technology, and infrastructure that can improve productivity and profitability. Initiatives such as the Anchor Borrowers' Program (ABP) and Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) have been implemented to provide farmers with access to credit at affordable rates, thereby promoting agricultural growth.
2. Agricultural value chain financing: Financial institutions and development partners are increasingly providing

financial products tailored to different stages of the agricultural value chain, including production, processing, marketing, and distribution. This helps to address financing challenges along the value chain and promote value addition, market access, and income generation for farmers and agribusinesses.

3. Digital financial solutions: The adoption of mobile money services, digital payment platforms, and financial technology (fintech) solutions has played a significant role in expanding financial inclusion in rural areas and among smallholder farmers. Digital financial services enable farmers to access credit, savings, insurance, and other financial products, improving their financial resilience and empowering them to invest in their agricultural activities.

4. Risk management and insurance: Agricultural insurance and risk management tools are essential for mitigating risks related to weather events, pests, diseases, market fluctuations, and other uncertainties faced by farmers. Access to agricultural insurance products, index-based insurance, and risk-sharing mechanisms can help farmers manage risks and protect their investments, thereby promoting agricultural growth

and sustainability.

In conclusion, financial deepening in Nigeria's agricultural sector is key to unlocking the sector's potential for economic growth, poverty reduction, and food security. By expanding access to finance, promoting investment in value chains, leveraging digital financial solutions, and enhancing risk management mechanisms, Nigeria can further facilitate the growth and development of its agricultural sector, contributing to overall economic progress and social

2.2 Theoretical Literature

This section reviews supply-leading theory and demand-following theory. This study is however, anchored on the supply leading theory.

2.2.1 Supply - Leading Theory

Schumpeter (1934), in his supply-leading hypothesis opined that it is development in the financial sector that brings about growth and development in the economy. According to this theory, an efficient financial system will undoubtedly increase the economy's effectiveness and promote savings mobilization, resource transfer from conservative sectors to more modern growth-inducing sectors, thus leading to the creation of additional liquidity, and capital accumulation. The supply-leading theory opined that financial

deepening boost economic growth.

On the basis of supply leading hypothesis, Ejinkonye R. Chinwoke et al (2024) conducted a study on the impact of financial deepening on Agricultural output in Nigeria using credit to private sector (% of GDP); broad money supply (% of GDP); prime lending rate; savings rate and total savings (% of GDP) on agricultural output as financial deepening indicators concludes that financial development contributed to agricultural output in Nigeria within the period reviewed thus leading to economic growth. Also, on the same theoretical framework, Emmanuel I.A. and Vivian A. O. (2022) discovered that money supply (M2), market capitalization and liquid liabilities have positive significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. Similarly, Ogbonna U.Godfrey (2022) conducted a study on Economic Growth and Financial Deepening in Nigeria; using Error Correction model concludes that development in the financial sector significantly affect growth in the economy. Key proponent of the supply leading hypothesis is Schumpeter (1911) and the idea is supported by scholars such as Calderon and Liu (2003), Gurley and Shaw (1967).

2.2.2 Demand-Following Hypothesis

Robinson (1952) argues in his demand-

following finance hypothesis that it is development in the economy that triggers financial development. The demand following theory opined that economic activity propels financial institutions such as banks to finance enterprises. Thus, where enterprises lead, finance follows. This hypothesis view is that the development of the financial markets is merely a lagged response to economic growth. This implies that any early efforts to develop financial markets might lead to a waste of resources which could be allocated to more useful purposes in the early stages of growth. As the economy advances, this triggers an increase demand for more financial services and thus leads to greater financial development.

Following the demand following hypothesis, Odeniran and Udejaja (2010) explored the causality between Financial Development and Economic Growth in Nigeria, The result revealed the existence of bidirectional relationship between financial development and economic growth. Similarly, Unalmis (2002) examined causality between Financial Deepening and Economic Growth in Turkey, the study found the existence of bidirectional causality between financial deepening and economic growth in the

long run.

Omotor (2007), in his study of “Financial Development and Economic Growth: Empirical Evidence from Nigeria” established that financial development and growth has one-way causality. The study used annual data from Nigeria over the period 1970-2002 to construct a multivariate vector auto regression (VAR) model and Granger Causality Tests using real GDP, net domestic credit, net investment, trade openness and human capital investment. The result of analysis indicated that the causality relationship runs from the economic growth to financial development.

2.3 Empirical Literature:

1. Ejinkonye R. Chinwoke et al (2024) explored the impact of financial deepening on Agricultural output in Nigeria. The study adopted financial deepening indicators of credit to private sector (% of GDP); broad money supply (% of GDP) and prime lending rate on agricultural output. Their findings showed that: CPS/GDP had insignificant effect on AGO; M3/GDP had insignificant effect on AGO; PLR had significant effect on AGO. The result showed that indicators of financial deepening are jointly significant to growth in agricultural output in Nigeria under the reviewed

period.

2. Jolaiya, Olatubosun Felix (2024), examined the impact of financial deepening on domestic investment in Nigeria. The study covered a period of 2005-2022. The dependent variable was domestic investment (DI) while the independent variables were financial deepening indicators (broad money supply, private sector credits, and stock market capitalization). The study employed the ARDL technique to analyze the data. The findings revealed that the three indicators of financial deepening have positive significant impact on domestic investment. The study thus recommends that government through monetary authority to further deepen the financial sector to drive economic growth.

3. Ezeunwa Justice, Lucky Orlu, and Young N. Geoffrey (2023) assessed the impact of financial deepening on poverty in Nigeria for a period of 1990-2020. The variables employed are per capita income, money supply, domestic credit to private sector and interest rate. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression technique was used in data analysis. The findings indicated that that there is a positive significant relationship between financial deepening and poverty in Nigeria, Also, the result showed that money supply

has a positive significant effect on poverty in Nigeria. The study recommended that the CBN should maintain increase in broad money supply(M2) and domestic credit to private sector so as to a reduce in Poverty level in Nigeria.

4. Abbas Abdullahi Marafa (2022) conducted a study on the impact of financial deepening on economic growth in Nigeria with annual time series data between 1986 and 2020. The study used Autoregressive Distributed Lagged (ARDL) bounds test approach for co-integration test. The ARDL short-run result affirms the existence of a long-run relationship between the variables in the model. The result of both the short-run and long-run analysis indicated that the coefficient of total bank asset ratio and market capitalization ratio are positive and statistically, while the coefficients of activity variables (economic volatility and stock market liquidity) are negative and statistically significant. The result of the Granger causality test indicates that there is a unidirectional causality running from economic growth to financial deepening variables, thereby supporting the demand-following hypothesis. The study recommends for regulatory bodies to enhance the operations and activities of the financial

sector; effectively expand and improve the credit channels in favor of the real and productive sectors of the economy; and strengthen policies that will improve the institutional and legal framework for stock market operations

5. Emmanuel I. Ajudua¹ and Vivian A. Odishika (2022) evaluated the impact of financial deepening on Nigeria's economic growth for the period 1986 to 2020. The time series data were analyzed using the Auto-regressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) and the Error Correction Mechanism estimation techniques. The findings indicate that money supply (M2), market capitalization and liquid liabilities have positive significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria while credit to private sector has no significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria during the reviewed period. The study thus recommends upward review of interest rate on savings deposits in order to induce customers to save more money with commercial banks so as to boost investment in the country.

6. Okafor et al (2021) examined financial deepening and Nigeria's economic growth using Granger causality, Johansen Cointegration, and error correction model for the data analysis. The study adopted financial deepening indicators of capital market

capitalization (% of GDP), financial depth and ratio of credit to the private sector to GDP. The findings showed that financial deepening indicators, particularly bank-based financial depth have a favorable and significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth.

7. In a similar manner, Sylvester Ohiomu and Blessing O. Oligbi (2020) analyzed the impact of financial sector development on economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2018. The study adopted ARDL model for the analysis of the variables. The study used capital market capitalization, ratio of total savings to GDP and insurance indicators as financial deepening indicators. The results showed that the financial sector development indicators have long run relationship with economic growth. The study recommended that the Government should strengthen the money and capital markets for optimal development to speed up financial development and economic growth in the country.

8. Nwakobi, Oleka, and Ananwude (2019) investigated the effectiveness of financial deepening on economic growth and development in Nigeria for a period of 1986 to 2018. They sourced their data from CBN statistical bulletins and fact books of the Nigerian Stock

Exchange (NSE). The study used financial deepening indicators of market capitalization and money supply as a ratio of GDP as their variables. The study adopted the ARDL approach and granger causality test for their analysis. The study revealed that economic growth does not granger cause financial deepening in Nigeria.

9. Karimo and Ogbonna (2017) evaluated the direction of causality between financial deepening and economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1970 to 2013. The study used financial deepening indicators of money supply, credit to private sector and market capitalization as a ratio of GDP. The study adopted the Toda–Yamamoto augmented Granger causality test and results showed that the financial deepening in Nigeria follows the supply leading hypothesis. The study recommended that CBN should encourage commercial banks to increase credit to the private sector so as to boost economic growth.

10. Nwanna and Chinwudu (2016) examined financial deepening and economic growth in Nigeria between 1985 and 2014. The study used financial deepening indicators of money supply, market capitalization, private sector credit and financial savings. The study used ordinary least square (OLS)

econometric techniques. The result affirmed that financial deepening indicators have positive significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The study recommends policies that will enhance banking sector and capital market to play a key role in the nation development process

3.1 Research Design

Morgan L. Stephen (2014) defines research design as the conceptual framework that guides the research process. This study adopts the ex-post facto research design as it deals with event that had taken place and secondary data were readily available for collection. Growth in Agricultural sector was employed as the dependent variables, while financial depth, financial access and financial efficiency served as the explanatory variables. The model was estimated using Auto Regressive Distributed lag (ARDL). Time series data of a sample period of thirty three years were used. To avoid the issue of non stationarity of data, unit root test was carried out by employing the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test.

3.2 Data Collection

Data of variables of interest which is data on growth in Agriculture was

obtained from World Bank Development Indicators (WDI). While data on the major indicators of financial deepening of financial depth, financial access and financial efficiency were sourced from IMF data base and CBN Statistical Bulletins for the period 1990-2023 and used for the empirical analysis.

3.3 Model Specification

The functional relationship between the endogenous variable and its explanatory variables of this study was anchor on the theory of supply leading hypothesis by Schumpeter (1934) and expressed in line with the analytical framework of Jolaiya, Olatubosun Felix (2024) and Okafor et al (2021)), who carried out an analytical impact of financial deepening on economic growth in Nigeria using market capitalization, financial depth and credit to private sector as proxies for financial deepening. However, in this study, modification was done in terms of extension of scope and inclusion of other variables like growth in agricultural sector (GAS), Financial Depth (FD) Financial Access (FA), and Financial Efficiency (FE), that is:

$$GAS = f(FD, FA, FE)$$

(3.1)

The generalized ARDL Regression Model is specified as:

$$Y_t = a_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + a_j Y_{t-j} + \beta_0 X_t + \beta_k X_{t-j} + e_t \quad (3.2)$$

The time series is represented by $t = 1,$

2..., 33 and it goes from 1990 to 2023. Y_t represents the endogenous variable (GAS) and, j is the maximum lag length chosen. Consequently, the ARDL Specification for the study is given as:

$$GAS = \alpha_i + \beta_1 FD_{t-j} + \beta_2 FA_{t-j} + \beta_3 FE_{t-j} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (3.3)$$

Since there is co-integration among the variables, the error correction form of model 3.3 is given as:

$$\Delta GAS_t = \delta + \sum_{i=1}^p a_1 \Delta FD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q a_2 \Delta FA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q a_3 \Delta FE_{t-i} + \&ECT_{t-i} + e_t$$

Where: GAS =

Growth in Agricultural Sector as dependent variable **FD** = Financial Depth, **FA** = Financial Access and **FE** = Financial Efficiency (all serve as explanatory variables). δ = speed of adjustment (with a negative sign, it shows convergence, while positive is no convergence).

$\alpha_1 - \alpha_3$ are short run coefficients, $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ captures long run relationships, δ represents the intercept or constant, μ is the error term and Δ represents the difference operator. The a priori expectations require that increase in financial depth; increase in financial access and increase in financial efficiency will lead to increase in growth

in the agricultural sector of the economy. The symbolic representations of the relationship based on the a priori expectations are as follows: $b_1 > 0$, $b_2 > 0$, and $b_3 > 0$,

3.4 Method and Techniques of Data Analysis

The auto regressive distributive lag (ARDL) technique developed by Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001) was adopted to estimate the empirical relationship between financial deepening and agricultural growth in Nigeria. The selection of ARDL is based on its distinctive attributes to estimate variables especially when the data for analysis are not all stationary and there is likelihood of mixed order of integration. The study employed time series data which necessitated stationarity tests. Sequentially, the Unit Root Test was conducted and it was followed by the Co-integration procedure to examine whether long run relationship exist between variables of

financial deepening. This study applied the Augmented Dickey and Fuller (1981) method for the unit root test in each of the variables to determine their respective order of integration. Evidence of unit root in the series necessitated the application of the bound cointegration test as proposed by Pesaro, Shin and Smith (2001) to ascertain whether the variables have long-run relationship. The study found that the variables exhibit a long run relationship, meaning that they can be combined in a linear form and even if there are shocks in the short run, they would converge with time in the long run. Hence, both the long run and short run models were estimated.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1: Descriptive statistics of the series

4.1.1 Trend Analysis of Financial Sector Deepening Indicators and Agricultural sector Growth in Nigeria

Source: Author’s Computation based on data extracted from the WDI

Source: Author’s Computation based on data extracted from the WDI

The descriptive analysis of the trends of the variables in the model shows that the growth of Agricultural sector depicted in Figure 4.1, witnessed an increase from 1990 to 1983 before decreasing to 21.4% in 2000. It fluctuated between 2006 and 2022 at a declining rate. It attained a record low of

(19.9) in 2014 and a record high of 37% in 2002. Since then, the sector has been growing at a declining rate. Figure 4.2, shows the trends of financial access, it shows that it witnessed a constant increase from 1990 to 1996 before maintain a steady growth till 2008. It declined drastically from 2008

and become maximized of 0.5% till 2023. Financial efficiency shown in Figure 4.2 fluctuated between 1990 and 2023. It witnessed a record low of 0.45% in 2011 and a record high of 0.65% in 2022. Lastly, financial depths as

indicated in figure 4.2 witness an increase between 1990 and 1996. It attained a record low of 0.05% in 1998 and a record high of 0.11% in 2007. It fluctuated between year 2010 and 2018 before experiencing increase till date.

4.1.2 Basic Descriptive Statistics Result

Table 4.1: Descriptive statistics of the series

	AGRIC, SECTOR GROWTH	FINANCIAL. ACCESS	FINANCIAL. DEPTH	FINANCIAL. EFFICIENCY
Mean	24.23716	0.465054	0.047055	0.517814
Median	23.79279	0.501671	0.049966	0.500196
Maximum	36.96508	0.507519	0.111617	0.654383
Minimum	19.99025	0.264885	0.015215	0.387831
Std. Dev.	3.663617	0.073115	0.022367	0.082776
Skewness	1.654663	-1.765065	0.266168	0.14377
Kurtosis	6.357215	4.596733	3.228368	1.720566
Jarque-Bera	31.48193	21.26612	0.475339	2.436144
Probability	0	0.000024	0.788463	0.2958
Sum	824.0636	15.81182	1.599873	17.60568
Sum Sq. Dev.	442.9289	0.176409	0.016509	0.22611
Observations	34	34	34	34

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

Evaluations from Table 4.1 reveal that growth in Agriculture averaged 24.3 percent between 1990 and 2023. This is suggestive that on the average about one third of the total Nation's Gross domestic product is accounted for by the Agricultural sector. The minimum and maximum values of growth in Agricultural sector are 19.9 and 36.9 respectively. Financial access ranged from 0.3 to 0.5, financial depth ranged from 0.02 to 0.1. While financial

efficiency averaged 0.05 percent between 1990 and 2023 and ranged from 0.38 to 0.65. Further to this, the probability values of the Jarque-Bera statistics of all the variables except financial access are more than 0.05, indicating that at 5% level, the errors in the variables are normally distributed.

4.2 Data Analysis

In this section, pre-estimation diagnostics tests and estimated cointegration models as well as the

associated post-estimation tests are presented and explained.

4.2.1 Pre-estimation Diagnostics Tests (Multicollinearity Test)

This multicollinearity test is undertaken in this study using variance inflation factor. The VIF coefficients are reported in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Variance Inflation Factor coefficient

	Coefficient	Uncentered	Centered
Variable	Variance	VIF	VIF
FINANCIAL_ACCESS	51.65099	60.88737	1.426488
FINANCIAL_DEPTH	671.0295	9.642966	1.73433
FINANCIAL_EFFICIENCY	57.21897	83.69018	2.025478
AGRICULTURE_SECTOR_GROWTH	0.446744	110.5869	2.399217

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

Table 4.2 shows the centered variance inflation factor coefficients for the variables. It was seen that multicollinearity is not a major issue in the model because the coefficient of the centered variance inflation factor for each of the variables is not too high (i.e. value of VIF <5) to suggest severe

multicollinearity. It therefore follows that the explanatory variables can be regressed together without problem of indeterminate coefficients and high variance.

4.2.2 Unit Root Test

The unit root test results are summarized in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Summary of ADF unit root test results

ADF Unit root test results					
Variable	Levels test results		First Difference test results		
	t-stat.	5% critical value	t-stat.	5% critical value	Order of integration
GAS	-1.92	-2.97	-6.49	-2.97	I(1)
FA	-3.03	-2.97	-3.45	-3.56	I(0)
FD	-3.17	-3.56	-6.06	-3.56	I(1)
FE	-1.43	-2.97	-5.29	-3.56	I(1)

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

Table 4.3 tabulated the unit test results for each of the variables. The leftmost

part shows the test results at levels while the rightmost part shows the test

results at first difference. It was found that financial Access is stationary at levels. The unit root result shows that the variables are mixed integrated and thus, can enter into the ARDL model upon verification of long run

relationship among them from the cointegration test.

4.2.3 Cointegration Test

The Bound test proposed by Pesaro, Shin and Smith (2001) methodology was applied.

Table 4.4: Bound results for model Agricultural model

Series: GAS, FA FD FE				
F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis		
		No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value OF	SIGNIFICANT	LOWER BOUND	UPPER BOUND
	F-stat		I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	8.723765	10%	3.47	4.45
K	3	5%	4.01	5.07
		2.5%	4.52	5.62
		1%	5.17	6.36

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

The bound test result of growth in Agriculture shows that the variables have long run relationship as the F-statistics value is greater than the 5% critical value of the upper bound.

The cointegration models that portray the long run behavior of the variables are estimated using Auto regressive distributive lag (ARDL) model with the specification of both the short and long run short forms of equation results.

4.3 Estimation of the Cointegration Model

Table 4.5: ARDL SHORT AND LONG RUN (MODEL ONE): GAS

Short Run Equation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(GAS(-1))	0.265656	0.153909	1.726056	0.0998
D(FIN_ACC))	0.344670	0.168567	2.044712	0.0543
D(FIN_DEP)	-23.29563	28.20142	-0.826045	0.4185
D(FIN_DEP(-1))	81.42517	32.80320	2.482233	0.0221
D(FIN_DEP(-2))	59.27024	29.67386	1.997389	0.0596
D(FIN__EFF_)	-4.224713	10.97506	-0.384938	0.7043
D(FIN__EFF_(-1))	-22.27370	10.15264	-2.193883	0.0402
CointEq(-1)*	-0.347060	0.139203	-2.493189	0.0215
R-squared	0.520214	Mean dependent var		0.077541
Adjusted R-squared	0.374192	S.D. dependent var		3.086689
S.E. of regression	2.441818	Akaike info criterion		4.840999
Sum squared resid	137.1370	Schwarz criterion		5.211060
Log likelihood	-67.03548	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.961630
Durbin-Watson stat	1.967219			

Long Run Equation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FIN_ACC	56.44130	21.51884	2.622878	0.0163
FIN_DEP	-276.0092	132.7279	-2.079511	0.0506
FIN__EFF_	20.63928	25.97357	0.794626	0.4362

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

From the result of of ARDL regression results in Table 4.5 it was found that financial access has positive significant impact on growth in the agricultural sector. This finding is in agreement with the priori expectation that increase in financial access as an indicator of financial deepening will result to growth in agricultrue, thus leading to economic growth. Financial depth was significant but negative,while financial efficiency

was found to be insignificant to growth in agriculture during the sampled period. The ARDL Short run result shows that the coefficient of the error correction term (COINTEQ01) is -0.347060. The result is negative and significant at the 5% level of statistical significance meaning that 34.7% of the divergence from the long-run equilibrium is corrected each period.

4.4:Post-estimation Diagnostics

Tests

Serial correlation LM test, normality test

The post-diagnostic test includes: and stability test.

Table: 4.6 Autocorrelation test result for Agriculture model

Autocorrelation test result for Growth in Agriculture Model				
Dependent Variable =GAS				
F-statistic	1.03587	Prob. F(2,24)		0.3702
Obs*R-squared	2.542819	Prob. Chi-Square(2)		0.2804
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FIN_ACC	-7.49134	12.68606	-0.59052	0.5604
FIN_DEP	11.61671	27.71415	0.419162	0.6788
FIN_EFF	2.731029	9.421871	0.289861	0.7744
L2GAS	0.1566	0.252907	0.6192	0.5416
LGAS	0.102927	0.433134	0.237634	0.8142
C	-4.76114	8.992123	-0.52948	0.6013
RESID(-1)	0.004397	0.447605	0.009823	0.9922
RESID(-2)	-0.43289	0.331539	-1.3057	0.204
R-squared	0.079463	Mean dependent var		-2.11E-15
Adjusted R-squared	-0.18903	S.D. dependent var		2.349835
S.E. of regression	2.562319	Akaike info criterion		4.932021
Sum squared resid	157.5715	Schwarz criterion		5.298455
Log likelihood	-70.9123	Hannan-Quinn criter.		5.053483
F-statistic	0.295963	Durbin-Watson stat		1.994237
Prob(F-statistic)	0.948779			

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

The serial correlation LM test in Table 4.6 shows that growth in agriculture model is free from serial correlation at 5% level.

Figure 4.1: Plot of normality test for Agriculture model

Series: Residuals	
Sample 1990 2023	
Observations 34	
Mean	8.00e-17
Median	-0.006384
Maximum	0.094303
Minimum	-0.099465
Std. Dev.	0.055811
Skewness	-0.155407
Kurtosis	2.055965
Jarque-Bera	1.399393
Probability	0.496736

Source: E-views 12, Author's computation

From the normality test results illustrated in Figure 4.1 the errors in the models is normally distributed. This is because the associated probability value of the Jarque-Bera statistics is greater than 0.05.

Table: 4.7: Stability Test Result for Agriculture Model

The Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) of squares serves as the stability test.

This is represented in the figure below:

As shown in Table 4.7, the Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) of Squares line is within the 5% critical value bounds. Therefore, the estimates of the long-run model for

Agriculture is stable.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENTATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

The main objective of the study was to assess the impact of financial deepening on Agricultural growth in Nigeria between 1990 and 2023. The study utilizes Agricultural growth as dependent variable while financial deepening indicators of financial depth, financial access and financial efficiency as regressors. The result of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique shows that all the independent variables have significant relationship with growth in agriculture, except financial efficiency that had positive insignificant impact on agricultural growth. From the ARDL result, inference can be drawn that financial deepening had significant impact on agricultural growth in Nigeria during the reviewed period.

5.2 Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby provided for policy actions based on the outcomes of the study:

1. Monetary authorities in Nigeria especially CBN should implement policies that would boost financial inclusion so that Nigerian citizens will have easy access to affordable financial services that will impact

positively in the agricultural sector, thus leading to economic growth.

2. CBN should encourage commercial banks to increase extension of credit to farmers and private sector in order to boost Agricultural output in Nigeria.
3. Government at all level should formulate policies and programs that will encourage investment in Agricultural sector of the economy.

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